

MESO-SCALE MODELING OF TRIAXIAL BRAIDED TEXTILE UNDER BALLISTIC IMPACT

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ABSTRACT

In the current paper, meso-scale model methods based on yarn architecture of triaxial braided composites were employed to investigate its dynamic response in LS-DYNA. Numerical simulations were conducted on single layer braided textile. The dynamic response and energy absorption mechanism of triaxial braided textile under impact was discussed. The influence of friction action and boundary conditions was also addressed. It is found that the main response of triaxial braided textile under projectile impact are the transverse wave propagation, yarn tension, yarn fracture and pull-out successively. In the initial stage of impact, the yarns are still in the crimped state and the interaction force between the projectile and textile is very low. After the yarns are straighten, the interaction force and yarn strain energy increase rapidly and reach its maximum value before the yarn fracture. Yarn strain energy, yarn kinetic energy and friction sliding energy are the main energy absorption modes. The yarn strain energy and kinetic energy increase first and decrease later, while the sliding energy increase significantly in the process of perforation. The boundary constraint has evident influence on the deformation, interaction force and energy absorption of braided textile. The boundary conditions change the proportional relations of yarn internal energy and yarn kinetic energy. It also influences the distributions of strain energy of yarns in each direction. The friction factor has great influence on the ballistic performance. When the friction factor is smaller, the yarns are apt to sliding away and give rise to the deduction of energy absorption.

1 INTRODUCTION

In high bypass ratio turbofan engines, the fan casing is an extremely heavy structural component. The use of composite materials could significantly reduce the weight of the fan casing and improve the engine thrust-weight ratio. A successful example is GENx engine developed by GE aviation[1] whose

front fan casing employs the triaxial braided composites utilizing flattened large tow carbon fiber, which has advantages of lower manufacturing cost, improved damage resistance, and better through-thickness strength. Though many efforts have been focused on the mechanical properties and failure modes of triaxial braided composite [2-4], there are limited studies on its ballistic behavior. The complex fiber architecture and large unit cell size in triaxial braided composite materials present challenges for both understanding the deformation process and measuring reliable material properties, which also retard the application of this material.

Numerical techniques have been widely used to predict the response behaviors and the failure mechanisms of composites due to transverse impact loading. Simulations on impact behavior of triaxial braided composites are always based on simplifications of the fiber configuration. Xiao et al. ([5]) simulated the braided composite tube axial crush using shell elements based on a composite damage constitutive model (MAT58) in LS-DYNA, which could reproduce the softening behavior of the braided composite under monotonic compressive loading, but failed in subsequent unloading and tensile loading cycles. Based on the disadvantages observed, they developed an analog model and a coupled damage-plasticity constitutive model ([6]) to improve the prediction of the tube crush. Liu et al. [7] developed a continuum finite element model based on Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) model to obtain the time history of projectile velocity, displacement, penetration resistance force, and energy absorption during the impact process, and achieved good agreements with the experimental results. Besides the continuum modeling method, Cheng [8], Staniszewski [9], Li et al. [10], Goldberg et al. [11], Zhang et al. [12] and Cater et al. [13] developed a macro level finite element based model to simulate the mechanical and impact response of triaxial braided polymer matrix composites. In this method, the unit cell of the braided composite is modeled as a series of shell elements, where each element is modeled as a laminated composite. By defining the integration points of shell elements, the layer sequence and angle is able to be assigned easily, and ballistic model is capable of being analyzed with great efficiency.

Meso-scale model which contain matrix, fiber bundles and interfaces respectively has been employed to predict its mechanical properties and failure modes [14-16] as well as the size-dependent performance and edge effect [17-19]. However the meso-scale model is not practical when studying the ballistic behavior of structures. It is noticeable that in recent years the meso-scale model of woven fabrics originally proposed by Shockey [20] achieved extensive application in studying its ballistic response. Duan et al. [21-22], Chocorn et al. [23] and Nilakantan et al. [24-25] developed the yarn level model of plain weave fabrics and investigated the dynamic response of high strength plain weave fabric, explored its energy absorption mechanism and achieved good effect.

In the current paper, a meso-scale model methods based on yarn architecture of triaxial braided composites were employed to investigate its dynamic response in LS-DYNA. This model contains only fiber bundles component and neglect the contribution of matrix and the complex mechanical behavior of interface, which great reduce the modeling complication and make it possible to be used in structural impact analysis. Considering the main ballistic resistance are provided by fiber and the main purpose of this paper is to investigate the stress wave propagation and energy absorption of fibers in different directions, the simplification is reasonable. Numerical simulations were conducted on single layer braided textile in different boundary conditions. The dynamic response and energy absorption mechanism of triaxial braided textile under impact was discussed. The influence of friction action and boundary conditions was also referred to.

2 NUMERICAL MODELING

2.1 Geometry Model

Byun et al. [26] presented the photography section in different direction and proposed the assumptions on the yarn sections, as shown in Figure 1. To obtain the schematic of yarns, geometry parameters were defined:

The following parameters are defined to obtain the geometric relations: t_a , t_b , t_u =the thickness of axial yarns, braider yarns, and the unit cell, respectively; f_a =the aspect ratio of the axial yarn cross-section along the width directions; L_s =the repeat length of the braider-yarn undulation; r_u =the radius of the braider-yarn undulation; and ϕ =the yarn-crimp angle. Since the shape parameters of the axial yarn,

t_a and f_a , can be measured from the sample photomicrograph, the following parameters can be determined from the known quantities:

$$L_s = \frac{h}{\cos \theta} \quad (1)$$

$$t_b = \frac{t_u - t_a}{2} \quad t_h = \frac{t_u + t_a}{2} \quad (2)$$

Since the shape of the axial-yarn section is lenticular, the braider-yarn undulation on it can be assumed to be an arc. It can be shown that the arc angle is the same as the yarn-crimp angle. The radius of the braider-yarn undulation and the crimp angle can be expressed as a function of parameters, L_s and t_h :

$$r_u = \frac{(L_s / 2)^2 + t_h^2}{2t_h} \quad (3)$$

$$\phi = \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{L_s}{2r_u}\right) \quad (4)$$

Because of the regular shape of the axial-yarn cross-section, the area is calculated in the width direction of the sample. Denoting as the inner angle of the lenticular shape, the cross-sectional area of the yarn can be expressed as:

$$A_a = r_a^2(\alpha - \sin(\alpha_a)) \quad (5)$$

where

$$r_a = \frac{t_a}{4}(1 + f_a^2) = 2 \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{2f_a}{1 + f_a^2}\right) \quad (6)$$

Figure 1: Schematic yarn sections in the braider-yarn direction

The geometry parameters of triaxial braided composite with 12k T700 carbon fiber for both the axial and braided yarns can be referred, and calculated with above equations, as listed in Table1.

w/mm	h/mm	t_u/mm	t_a/mm	f_a	λ	$\phi/^\circ$	κ
3	10.5	0.82	0.38	5.28	1.0	11.42	0.77
L_s/mm	t_b/mm	r_u/mm	r_a/mm	$\alpha/^\circ$			
6	0.22	15.15	2.74	42.9			

Table1 the geometry parameter of tri-axial braided composite

According to the geometry assumption and parameters in Table1, the geometry model can be established for the 2D triaxial braided textile, as shown in Figure2. It contains the axial yarns in 0° direction, and the braided yarns in $\pm 60^\circ$ directions. In which the direction 1 denotes the -60° direction, direction 2 denotes the axial direction and direction 3 denotes the $+60^\circ$ direction. The textile has length of 63 mm and width of 48 mm. In the length direction, there are 6 unit cells while 16 unit cells in the width direction.

Figure3 presents the finite element model of triaxial braided textile of single layer and multi-layers. The yarns were meshed with 8-nodes hexahedron elements. 6 elements were defined in the yarn section width direction while 2 elements were defined in the yarn thickness direction. A total of 78239 elements were divided. The flat-ended cylinder projectile of Titanium alloy was employed to impact the braided textile. The projectile has diameter of 10 mm, height of 20 mm and weight of 6.9 g. There are 2640 elements for the projectile with mesh size 1 mm.

Figure 2: Geometry model of triaxial braided composite

Figure 3: High speed impact finite element model of Single layer triaxial braided textile

2.2 Material Model

The orthotropic elastic material model was employed for the solid yarns. The mechanical properties were obtained from the T700/8911 unidirectional composites[4], as listed in Table 2, where E , G , ν represents the elastic modulus, shear modulus and poisson's ratio; X_t , X_c , Y_t , Y_c represents the longitudinal tensile strength, longitudinal compressive strength, transverse tensile strength and transverse compressive strength; S denotes the shear strength.

E_1/Gpa	E_2/Gpa	E_3/Gpa	G_{12}/Gpa	G_{13}/Gpa	G_{23}/Gpa	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
135	11.41	11.41	7.92	7.92	7.92	0.33	0.33	0.49
ρ/kgm^{-3}	X_t/Mpa	X_c/Mpa	Y_t/Mpa	Y_c/Mpa	S/Mpa			
1550	2600	1422	60.3	241	94			

Table 2: The orthotropic elastic parameter for yarns

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Dynamic response of single layer textile

The damage pattern of textile impacted by projectile with different velocity is shown in Figure 4. It is indicated that when the projectile velocity is 40 m/s, the projectile rebounds and the textile is intact without any yarn fracture. When the impact velocity increasing to 50 m/s, the textile deforms severely and fracture emerge in the -60° yarn. The axial yarn was pushed away and 60° yarn maintained its integrity without breaking. As the impact velocity increase to 80 m/s, the projectile perforates the textile and yarns in all three directions were fractured. In the impact region, approximately circular hole was formed and fractured yarns were push out along the projectile exit direction.

Figure 4: The damage pattern of single layer textile

Taken the impact velocity of 80 m/s as example, the deformation characteristic of triaxial braided textile with 4 edges clamped were analyzed, as shown in Figure 5. It is seen that the round deformation area was formed in the fabric plane at 0.05 ms, which is caused by the transverse wave effect. The head of projectile was not completely contact with the fabric. For the orthogonal weave fabric, the transverse wave propagates faster along the weft yarn and wrap yarn than the other direction, thus typical diamond deformation area emerge. For tri-axial braided fabric, as the yarns in plane were distributed in the form of quasi-isotropic, thus the deformation area was in the approximately round shape.

As the projectile moves forward, the transverse wave propagates to the surrounding area and when it propagates to the edges, the projectile and textile is in complete contact and the textile below the projectile was in flat bottom. After that great tension deformation of yarns were generated in the action of clamped boundary and projectile impact. After 0.15 ms, the yarns directly below the projectile began to fracture and pushed out along the projectile exit direction. After the projectile impact, round hole in the size of projectile were left in the textile and damage pattern includes yarns fracture and unraveling.

Fig.6 presents the variation of projectile velocity, interaction force and the energy variation during impact process. It is found that the interaction time lasts about 0.2 ms for the textile with 4 edges clamped, which can be divided into several stages: before the transverse wave propagates to the boundary until 0.1 ms, the yarns is in crimped status. The projectile and the textile is not in complete contact and the resistance force is small and the projectile velocity decrease slowly. After that, the yarns are straighten from the original crimped status. The resistant force increase sharply and projectile velocity decrease greatly. Until 0.15 ms, the tensile deformation of yarns reaches its limit. After that, the interaction force decrease with the rupture of yarns and close to zero at 0.22 ms when

all yarns in the impact zone fractures. The projectile velocity maintains almost unchanged during the perforation process.

The projectile kinetic energy diminish continuously while the yarn kinetic energy and internal energy increase first and decrease later. The sliding energy increase monotonously on the other hand. Before 0.1 ms, the yarn internal energy and kinetic energy increase slowly due to its crimped condition. During the straighten process from 0.1 ms to 0.15 ms, the yarn strain energy increase rapidly to its maximum value. Because of the interlace of yarns, almost all yarns is under tensile action. The yarn internal energy consumed almost 60% of total projectile initial energy. After 0.15 ms, the primary yarns under projectile fractures gradually and the deformation of secondary yarns recovers. The yarn internal energy declines and kinetic energy adds a bit. The growth of sliding energy begin to play a role in the energy consumption mainly in the perforation process after 0.15 ms. The sliding energy due to friction consumed 65% of total energy.

Known from the analysis above, in the earlier stage of impact, the energy absorption is mainly in the form of yarn kinetic energy and internal energy. The interlace pattern of yarns promotes more yarns involving in the impact process and resist the penetration of projectile. After the primary yarn fracture and secondary yarns recovers form elastic deformation, friction sliding plays the dominating role in energy absorption.

Figure 5: the perforate process of single layer textile ($V_i=80$ m/s)

Figure 6: Impact response of braided textile ($V_i=80$ m/s): (a) projectile velocity (b) energy variation

3.2 Boundary conditions

It is already discovered that, boundary conditions plays an important role in the impact resistance ability and dynamic response. In this section, the dynamic response of triaxial braided textile is discussed. The same initial velocity of 80 m/s was employed. Figure 7 shows the impact damage of textile with only short edges (the left and right edges) clamped. It is obvious that the yarns in the free edges unraveling after the perforation of projectile. There exists a perforation hole in the center corresponding to the projectile geometry. Lateral sliding is observed in the yarns around the hole.

Figure 7: The impact damage of textile with 2 edges clamped

Figure 8 shows the deformation and damage process of textile under impact in the condition of 2 edges clamped. Before 0.15 ms, the main feature is the propagation of transverse propagation and the formation of sunken deformation in the impact surface. Because of the absence of constraint in the long edges (the upper and bottom edge), yarns which is in total free status move with the deformation of textile and unravel in the free edge. With the short edges clamped, the axial yarn is not constrained, thus the braid yarns plays the main role in the resist of projectile. Meanwhile, the interaction action lasts for a longer time and the projectile perforates the textile after 0.6 ms. Compared with the 4 edges clamped condition, the textile with 2 edges clamped is more free and scattered after impact.

Figure 9 shows the comparison of projectile velocity and interaction force in this two different boundary conditions. It is found that with the same initial velocity of 80 m/s, the projectile velocity descends quickly to 50.9 m/s when clamped all edges, while the projectile velocity decrease slowly to 32.3 m/s for 2 edges clamped. Consequently, the 2 edges clamped boundary can make the textile absorb more energy and resist the projectile movement effectively. The interaction force comes the maximum value of 1896 N at time 0.235 ms for the 2 edges clamped condition, while the maximum interaction force is 2296 N at 0.155 ms for the 4 edges clamped. The main impact process of 4 edges clamped sustains 0.23 ms while 0.46 ms for 2 edges clamped. Though the interaction force level is below that of 4 edges clamped, the interaction between the projectile and textile lasts longer time for 2 edges clamped condition. This is the main reason that the 2 edges clamped textile can absorb more energy and have lower residual velocity.

Figure 8: The impact process of single layer textile with 2 edges clamped ($V_i=80$ m/s)

Figure 10 presents the comparison of the variation of yarn internal and kinetic energy in two different conditions. In Figure 10(b), E_1, E_2, E_3 is the yarn internal energy with 4 edges clamped, and E_1', E_2', E_3' is yarn internal energy. When the textile is constrained in the short edges, the yarn internal energy enhances a bit, meanwhile the time reach to the maximum value postpone. This is because the yarns can move along the projectile movement and achieve the straightened status later. The yarn kinetic energy is almost consistent in two conditions. The symbol 1 denotes the braid yarns in -60° direction, and 2 denotes the axial yarn in 0° direction, and 3 denotes the braid yarn in 60°

direction. It is noticed that the energy absorption for the 3 direction is almost the same for 4 edges clamped, while the energy absorption by the axial yarns decrease significantly due to its unconstrained fact. Correspondingly, the internal energy of braid yarns boost obviously. Besides, the internal energy of axial yarns is small in the initial stage and increase later. For the 2 edges clamped, the braid yarns play the dominant role in preventing penetration. It is concluded that, the boundary conditions can influence the proportional relations between yarn internal and kinetic energy and change the distribution of internal energy in each directions.

Figure 9: Results of different boundary conditions ($V_i=80$ m/s) (a) projectile velocity (b) impact load

Figure 10: Results of different boundary conditions ($V_i=80$ m/s) (a) impact load (b) yarn internal energy

3.3 Influence of friction

Duan et al. discovered that the friction factor have great influence on the dynamic response of orthogonal woven fabric. In this section, the dynamic response of 2D triaxial braided textile was investigated with friction factor μ 0, 0.2 and 0.5 respectively at the same impact velocity of 80 m/s.

Figure 11 shows the variation of the projectile velocity and interaction force in three friction factors. It is found that the residual velocity is the highest (54.6 m/s) when the friction factor equals to zero, which means there is no friction action between projectile and yarns. Correspondingly, the projectile residual velocity is lowest (45.2 m/s) when the friction factor μ is 0.5. When the friction factor is 0, the maximum force is 1875 N, while the maximum force is 2465 N when the friction factor is 0.5. The maximum interaction force increases about 30% with the friction factor increase to 0.5.

Figure 12 shows the impact damage obtained with different friction factor. When the friction factor equals to zero, the punching hole is smaller with no breakage of axial yarn, while the punching hole is much larger when the friction factor and one axial yarn fractures below the projectile. This is because the friction action restricts the sliding of yarns, thus enhance the ballistic resistant capability and bring down the projectile residual velocity. Duan et al.[21] suggest the friction factor selecting value of 0.2,

which is employed in the simulation of this paper.

Figure 11 Results with different friction factor (a) projectile velocity (b) impact load

(a) $\mu=0$

(b) $\mu=0.5$

Figure 20: The comparison of textile damage with different friction factor

4 CONCLUSIONS

In current paper, meso-scale model of 2D triaxial braided textile was developed and employed to investigate its dynamic response and damage mechanism under projectile impact. Main conclusions were drawn:

(1) The main response of triaxial braided textile under projectile impact are the transverse wave propagation, yarn tension, yarn fracture and pull-out successively. In the initial stage of impact, the yarns are still in the crimped state and the interaction force between the projectile and textile is very low. After the yarns are straighten, the interaction force increase rapidly and reach its maximum value before the yarn fracture. The yarn strain energy achieves the maximum value as well.

(2) Yarn strain energy, yarn kinetic energy and friction sliding energy are the main energy absorption modes. The yarn strain energy and kinetic energy increase first and decrease later, while the sliding energy increase significantly in the process of perforation. The boundary constraint has evident influences on the deformation, interaction force and energy absorption of braided textile.

(3) The boundary conditions change the proportional relations of yarn internal energy and yarn kinetic energy. It also influence the distributions of strain energy of yarns in each direction. The friction factor has great influence on the ballistic performance. When the friction factor is smaller, the yarns are apt to sliding away and give rise to the deduction of energy absorption.

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